

May 1, 2025

JOURNAL OF
INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE
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International scientific and practical conference. International scientific and Applied Research. 10.05.2025.

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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O'ZBEKISTONDA INNOVATSION SIYOSATNING HOLATI VA RIVOJLANISHI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O'zbekistonda innovatsion siyosatning shakllanishi, mavjud holati va uni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan davlat strategiyalari tahlil qilinadi. Unda milliy innovatsion tizimni takomillashtirish, ilm-fan va ishlab chiqarish integratsiyasini kuchaytirish, yuqori texnologiyali sohalarga investitsiyalarni jalb etish, hamda startap-ekotizimini rivojlantirish kabi ustuvor yo'nalishlar yoritiladi. Shuningdek, innovatsion siyosatni amalga oshirishda duch kelinayotgan muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish bo'yicha takliflar ham keltiriladi. Maqola O'zbekistonning raqobatbardosh iqtisodiyotga o'tishida innovatsiyalar hal qiluvchi rol o'ynashini asoslaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbekiston, innovatsion siyosat, ilm-fan, texnologik rivojlanish, startap, investitsiya, innovatsion ekotizim, milliy innovatsion tizim, raqobatbardoshlik, modernizatsiya.

Bugungi kunda har qanday davlatning iqtisodiy o'sishi va ijtimoiy farovonligi, eng avvalo, innovatsion siyosatga bog'liq. Chunki innovatsiyalar iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiya qilishda, yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratishda, raqobatbardoshlikni oshirishda va zamonaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etishda hal qiluvchi omillardan biridir. O'zbekiston ham ushbu jarayondan chetda qolmayapti. Aksincha, so'nggi yillarda mamlakatimizda innovatsion rivojlanishga alohida e'tibor qaratilib, muhim islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistondagi innovatsion siyosatning bugungi holati, erishilgan natijalar hamda kelgusidagi rivojlanish istiqbollari haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Eng avvalo, ta'kidlash joizki, innovatsion siyosat bu – davlat tomonidan ilm-fan, texnologiya, ta'lim va ishlab chiqarish sohalarining o'zaro integratsiyasiga qaratilgan kompleks chora-tadbirlar yig'indisidir. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018-yil 21-sentabrdagi "Innovatsion rivojlanish vazirligini tashkil etish to'g'risida"gi farmoni bilan ushbu sohada yangi davr boshlandi. Mazkur qaror asosida Innovatsion rivojlanish vazirligi tashkil etilib, mamlakatning ilmiy-texnik salohiyatini rivojlantirish, innovatsion g'oyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash va ularni amaliyotga tatbiq etish maqsadida keng qamrovli ishlar boshlab yuborildi. [1]

O'zbekistonning "2030-yilgacha bo'lgan rivojlanish strategiyasi"da ham innovatsiyalar markaziy o'rinni egallagan. Ushbu strategiyada ilm-fan va texnologiyalarni ishlab chiqarish bilan integratsiyalash, startap loyihalarni rag'batlantirish, raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirish va yosh olimlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash masalalari belgilangan. Xususan, "Raqamli O'zbekiston – 2030" dasturi doirasida davlat xizmatlari tizimining raqamlashtirilishi, elektron hukumat

konsepsiyasi, sun'iy intellekt va ma'lumotlar bazalarini yaratish bo'yicha izchil ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. [2]

So'nggi yillarda bir nechta innovatsion markazlar, texnoparklar va ilmiy-tadqiqot laboratoriyalari faoliyatini boshladi. Masalan, "Yashnobod" texnoparki va "INNO" startap markazi bugungi kunda yoshlar orasida innovatsion g'oyalarni amaliyotga tadbiiq etishda muhim rol o'ynamoqda. Shuningdek, qator oliy ta'lim muassasalari huzurida ilmiy-innovatsion inkubatorlar tashkil etilib, ularning faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish maqsadida davlat granti va imtiyozlari yo'lga qo'yilgan.

Shuni alohida ta'kidlash lozimki, innovatsion siyosat faqat texnologik rivojlanish emas, balki ijtimoiy sohalarida ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Tibbiyot, ta'lim, ekologiya va energetika sohalarida amalga oshirilayotgan innovatsion loyihalar, bir tomondan, xizmat ko'rsatish sifatini oshirsa, ikkinchi tomondan, resurslardan tejamkorlik bilan foydalanishni ta'minlamoqda. Ayniqsa, tibbiyotda masofaviy konsultatsiyalar, diagnostika texnologiyalari, sun'iy intellekt yordamida tashxis qo'yish tizimlari keng joriy etilmoqda.

Albatta, mavjud yutuqlarga qaramay, innovatsion siyosatda hali yechimini kutayotgan muammolar ham talaygina. Eng avvalo, innovatsion infratuzilmaning barcha hududlarda bir xil rivojlanmaganligi, moliyalashtirish mexanizmlarining sustligi, ilmiy-tadqiqot natijalarini tijoratlashtirishdagi muammolar mavjud. Bundan tashqari, xalqaro hamkorlik, intellektual mulk huquqlari himoyasi va kadrlar tayyorlash tizimi ham doimiy e'tiborni talab qiladi.

Innovatsion siyosatning muvaffaqiyati, shubhasiz, inson kapitaliga bevosita bog'liq. Shu bois, bugungi kunda yoshlarning ilmiy salohiyatini oshirish, ularni ilm-fan va innovatsiyalar sohasiga jalb qilish maqsadida ko'plab loyihalar amalga oshirilmoqda. Xususan, "Ilm-fan va taraqqiyot" jamg'armasi, "Startap tashabbuslari" dasturi, "100 ta eng yaxshi innovatsion loyiha" tanlovi orqali iqtidorli yoshlar qo'llab-quvvatlanmoqda. [3]

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqib aytish mumkinki, O'zbekistonda innovatsion siyosat tizimli va izchil ravishda shakllanmoqda. Davlat tomonidan yaratilayotgan huquqiy va tashkiliy shart-sharoitlar, ta'lim va ilmiy muassasalar faoliyatining muvofiqlashtirilishi, tadbirkorlik subyektlariga berilayotgan imtiyozlar innovatsion faoliyatni yanada rivojlantirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Kelgusida esa, mazkur siyosatning samaradorligini oshirish uchun ilm-fan, ta'lim va ishlab chiqarish o'rtasidagi uzviy bog'liqlikni kuchaytirish, ilg'or xorijiy tajribalarni joriy etish, mahalliy kadrlar salohiyatini oshirish va innovatsion madaniyatni shakllantirish lozim bo'ladi.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytganda, innovatsion siyosat – bu faqat davlat yoki hukumatning ishi emas. Bu – butun jamiyat, ayniqsa, yosh avlodning mas'uliyatli ishtirokini talab qiladigan keng ko'lamlil harakatdir. O'zbekiston bugun innovatsion rivojlanish yo'lini tanlagan bo'lsa, bu yo'l faqat oldinga intilish, ilm va texnologiyaga tayanish orqali yuksak natijalarga olib keladi.

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